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HIPPARCOS reductions for multiple stars, XVIII
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This note is about the selection of systems for the 30-month CHF-generation, using the categorizations from apriori data in the 'Torino catalogue'.

1. Selection principles

The DS reduction methods in NDAC require that a subset of the Input Catalogue containing known and suspected non-singles is defined before the generation of Case History Files can be started. Further reductions can only be made from the CHF:s for these selected objects, and it is of course important that the selection is made carefully and systematically. (It would of course be ideal to make CHF:s for *all* stars, but this exceeds the present disk-storage capabilities at Lund Observatory while probably increasing the 'double star yield' rather marginally). The basic problem is to give for each HIC-number a 'category' (single, suspect, double, multiple). Furthermore, two (or 3) HIC-numbers sometimes make up one '2(3)-pointing' system, and this association has to be made also *before* the CHF-generation.

Obviously, CHF:s have to be derived for all 'known' doubles and multiples, but the specification of these is a far from trivial problem, given the great variety of systems, and the incompleteness of the data available. In fact, this has turned out to be one of the most laborious and error-prone tasks of the entire DS reduction process. It is not sufficient to know that a star is 'double' or 'multiple', but the actual separations and magnitude-differences determine if and how the multiplicity will be observable and analyzable. It is very difficult to make 'automatic' rules for this selection and categorization, because crucial data are often missing or of poor quality. Each time one is checking *some* aspect of the selections, several tens of system that fail to conform to the 'standard' pop out. After that particular problem is solved (sometimes manually, 'star by star'), tens of others fail in some other respect, and the process can apparently be repeated *ad infinitum*... Also, the original Input Catalogue (and its Annex 1) have been supplemented by other sources, in several iterations. It is therefore not very surprising that NDAC and FAST had rather different sets of 'known doubles' for the 12- and 18-month solutions. Hopefully, the common use of the compilation made in Torino by Pannunzio et al. will improve the situation. Even now, the Torino-catalog is more comprehensive than NDAC's 'updated IC', and with the promised inclusion of an up-to-date WDS, it will be even better.

Still, the categorization is complex. After much experimenting, I have decided to include most of the known components even if they are 'impossibly' faint, because the existing photometric data are generally of poor quality. The separations are more reliable, and it seems safe to exclude any component more than 30 arcsec from its primary, given that the IFOV attenuation at 30 arcsec is more than 6 magnitudes (cf. NDAC/LO/147). Even when only this simple separation-limit is applied, the practical division of the 'known' HIC-entries into 'double' or 'multiple' systems (with

1, 2 or 3 HIC-numbers to a ‘system’) is not very straightforward. For the multiples, in particular, there are a lot of problems. To be on the safe side, more than one (non-HIC) component within 30 arcsec of a primary makes a single-pointing multiple, and any extra component within 30 arcsec of the primary *or* the secondary of a 2-pointing double makes it a 2-pointing multiple. To be sure, many of these systems will in practice be solvable as doubles, but in my a priori categorization, they count as multiples. Also, it is sometimes difficult to decide automatically about the correct ‘pointing-strategy’, that is, which HIC-numbers shall be combined to one ‘system’. (The codes in the HIC are not always useable. As a very simple example, two separations AB and AC may be both above 30 arcsec, but the resulting BC double may be observable).

Then, there is the equally important question how to flag the ‘suspected non-singles’. There are two major inputs to this flagging, first a ‘histogram’ showing the statistics (over the mission) of the misfit of a three-parameter IDT model (valid only for singles) versus a five-parameter one (valid for any object). The raw histogram is translated into indices T_h and T_t , higher values corresponding to ‘disturbed’ systems. Secondly, the parameter T_m (which is simply the difference between AC and DC magnitude determinations) is used, again with positive values for non-single objects. As a first step, these indices are corrected by empirical ‘magnitude-equations’, ensuring that their distribution for ‘single stars’ (=all stars without a priori multiplicity information) is reasonably independent of the magnitude.

Originally, I then used a linear combination of all three indices as a combined criterion T_c . After some further experiments, I have found that the T_h is almost redundant, and that it is also unduly sensitive to magnitude variability. Therefore, for the present, the flagging criterion is given by $T_c = T_m + C(Hp) * T_t$, with a magnitude-dependent coefficient $C(Hp) = 0.005 + 0.00033 * (Hp - 8)$. (Several other versions have been tried, including defining ‘excluded’ areas in the T_t/T_m -plane, using logical combinations of T_m and T_t criteria and so on, but in all cases the T_m criterion is clearly the dominating one).

In all the flagging-experiments, it is necessary to have some ‘calibration’ doubles and singles. It is difficult to find enough ‘true’ singles, thus I have used the whole IC (known doubles excluded) as containing ‘mostly’ singles. Then I have a rather large number of (18-month) solutions for known systems, and the principle is to try to flag as many of these solutions as possible with a criterion flagging as few of the singles as possible. I try to flag the *same* proportion of these doubles at each magnitude, and this requires a *variable* percentage (with magnitude) of the singles to be flagged. In practice, this is difficult to achieve, mostly because different samples of solutions give different criteria. There is e.g. a definite variation in the flagging-efficiency with separation. Close to one or two slit-periods, less doubles get flagged, which can be seen clearly when results for 2-4 arcsec separation are compared with larger or smaller values. In the results below, a mean over the whole interval 0.1 to 10 arcsec is used.

For the flagging-statistics, one wants to define in some way the ‘difficulty’ of a solution. I have used for many years a parameter Δm_{eff} to this effect, but I have now redefined it to fit better to the real data (instead of basing it on the old simulations). The present definition

$$\Delta m_{\text{eff}} = \begin{cases} dHp - 34. \lg(\rho/0.112) & \rho < 0.10 \text{ arcsec} \\ dHp - 2.4 \lg(\rho/0.50) & 0.10 < \rho < 0.50 \text{ arcsec} \\ dHp & \rho \geq 0.50 \text{ arcsec} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

gives *very* roughly a similar astrometric error for given values of H_p and Δm_{eff} . The coefficients given are not very well-determined, however, and rather different slopes are necessary to give constant *photometric* sigmas. For stars fainter than $H_p = 9.5$, I also add a simplistic $H_p - 9.5$ to eq. (1), correcting partially for the magnitude-limit of the instrument. For a majority of doubles, Δm_{eff} is simply the magnitude difference between the components, and a range 2-4 is typical for the new discoveries by Hipparcos. I therefore use the number of solutions with Δm_{eff} in this range that gets flagged by the 'suspected non-single' criterion, see below.

2. The known doubles

For the 'known doubles', my present count ('Torino-catalogue' plus the CCDM-extension by Dommangeat and Nys) is 10582 single-pointing and 937 2-pointing doubles. The first figure has changed quite a bit over the years, and it will certainly increase with an updated WDS. The major increase since my 18-month CHF:s is for doubles with separations 10-30 arcsec but only a single IFOV-pointing. These are not explicitly indicated as double in the HIC, but the components are listed in Annex 1, and they should obviously have been included before. (Many of them are listed in my 18-month CHF:s as 'suspected non-singles'. With such large separations, they are impossible to solve by the standard SEEKDBL program, and ended up with spurious smaller separations). The Torino-catalog (Pannunzio et al.) contains all CHARA Catalogue (1988) speckle-pairs, even when only an upper limit to the separation is given. I require a 'known double' to have a separation above 0.05 arcsec, however, which reduces the number of new doubles to a few hundred, most of which were actually already in my files.

The 'known multiples' are *not* well-defined. At present, 832 single-pointing, 194 two-pointing and 4 three-pointing systems are listed, but as explained above, the criteria used for inclusion are probably too liberal. Many of these systems will in practice get good double-star solutions, as has been 'accidentally' verified in a few cases where they were previously classified and solved as doubles. True multiple-star solutions will certainly also be obtained, but the solution-programs are still under development.

3. The suspected non-singles

For the 'suspects', it is important to realize that the photometric calibration used to derive the AC and DC magnitudes have a rather large influence on the results. For the original 18-month CHF:s, there was an uncorrected bias in T_m , giving too many suspects at faint magnitudes. With partially corrected data, but still using the 'old' photometric calibration, I have ended up with the following (very ad hoc!) form for the flagging-limit as function of the H_p -magnitude

$$T_{\text{lim}}(H_p; \tau) = \begin{cases} \tau_1 \exp\left[-\frac{(H_p-5)^2}{3.0}\right] + \tau_2 & (H_p < 9.0) \\ \tau_1 \exp\left[-\frac{(H_p-5)^2}{3.0}\right] + \tau_2 - \tau_3/4 + \tau_3(H_p - 9.5)^2 & (H_p > 9.0) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where the τ_3 -term is only applied for $H_p > 9.5$. With constants $\tau_1 = 0.016$, $\tau_2 = 0.024$, $\tau_3 = 0.016$, this gives the reasonable statistics in Table1, flagging a total of 13647 stars (about as many as the known non-singles). The point to notice is the reasonably constant proportion of doubles included, requiring an increased fraction of the brightest and faintest 'singles' to be selected.

Table 1. The numbers and percentages flagged of ‘DS1’ ($\Delta m_{\text{eff}} = 2.0 - 3.0$) and ‘DS2’ ($\Delta m_{\text{eff}} = 3.0 - 4.0$) solutions, in various magnitude intervals. The column ‘Sing’ gives the corresponding fraction of ‘a prio singles’ flagged.

H_p	N(DS1)	DS1(%)	N(DS2)	DS2(%)	Sing(%)
<5	24	100	26	100	18.8
5-7	155	100	131	98	11.9
7- 8	290	100	227	94	10.6
8- 9	497	100	377	95	10.1
9-10	350	100	257	93	17.4
>10	179	97	66	94	15.4

Unfortunately, the above ‘proportion flagged’ is not the whole truth. One has also to take into account the actual proportion of the flagged ones that get a good solution. This can not be as easily investigated, because the sample of known doubles used above is just those for which a solution was actually obtained. Some very rough estimates may be had by using *all* stars with known a priori parameters, but the large uncertainties in the Δm :s makes detailed selections according to Δm_{eff} meaningless. From some such experiments, it seems that the proportion of solved systems is highest (> 85%) in the interval $H_p = 7 - 10$, decreasing to less than 70% for the brightest and faintest stars. These figures are only illustrative, however, because the sample of doubles is so poorly defined. The success-rate should also increase when more observations are included.

For the selection of a sample of ‘bona-fide singles’, I have used the same form for T_{lim} , only taking an interval in the τ_i such that the objects selected fall around the median of the T_c -distribution at each H_p . I take thus a ‘bona-fide single’ to be an object with a T_c above $T_{\text{lim}}(0.003, 0.0068, 0.003)$ but below $T_{\text{lim}}(0.004, 0.0080, 0.004)$, which flags 5014 objects.

4. Conclusions

The next round of (30-month) CHF-generation will either be a ‘preliminary’ or a ‘definite’ one (with the final photometric calibration). In the first case, it will contain approximately the number of CHF:s listed above, viz. : 13647(susp) + 5014(b.f. singles) + (10582+937) (dbls) + (832 + 194 + 4) (multiples) = 31210 Case History Files, involving 13647+5014+10582+1874+832+388+12=32349 individual HIC-numbers. This is about the present ‘practical’ limit, and hopefully, most of the solvable non-singles will be included. This will soon be superceded by a ‘final’ 30-month CHF-generation, using the final photometric calibration *and* hopefully the updated Washington Catalogue. The numbers will then inevitably change, especially the actual list of suspects. Any such changes necessitate a new extraction of the FOVC-data to use, and my original hope that the selections could at some point be ‘fixed’ is probably not realistic. (I am ‘fixing’, however, in one respect the selections by giving each object that has at any time been among the known or suspected non-singles a unique number, serving as the record-number in the files with a priori-data and solution results. This recent ‘administrative’ modification should make future NDAC/FAST-comparisons and extractions of partial results somewhat easier.)